

DETECTING VIRAL PATHOGENS WITH HUMAN INFECTION CAPACITY IN ANIMAL FARMS

FLUFET MISSION

FLUFET stand for Fluid Detection of viruses by graphene-based field effect transistor microarrays. The goal is to create and evaluate a proof-of-concept prototype for a rapid, fully automated detection device designed for continuous surveillance of a wide range of viruses on animal farms.

VIRAL RISKS IN FARMS

FLUFET focuses on the detection of viruses with potential for transmission between animals and humans.

AVIAN FLU (H5N1)

- 2003-2023, more than **860** human cases reported.
- The **53%** of the patients died.
- More than **58 M** poultry were culled.

SWINE FLU

- Nearly **1.4 B** people were infected.
- More than **400,000** of the patients died.
- Economic loss of approximately **\$3 B**.

COVID-19 (SARS-COV-2)

- Approximately **770 M** cases worldwide.
- Nearly **6,95 M** of those infected died.
- Global economic contraction of **\$15 B** in GDP.

WHY IN FARMS?

The high density of animals on farms and their constant interaction with humans facilitate the spread of diseases, mutations and the emergence of zoonoses.

- ZOONOTIC ORIGIN
75%
of emerging diseases
- YEAR 2023
2 billion
cases worldwide caused
by zoonotic diseases
- DISEASES RESULTED
IN YEAR 2023
3 million
deaths worldwide

FLUFET TECHNOLOGY

Bio-inspired FLUFET uses human receptors embedded in graphene layer to detect and classify virus through electronic changes.

FLUFET INNOVATION

FLUFET not only improves detection capabilities, but also sets a new standard for zoonotic disease surveillance. This technological evolution is essential to strengthen sanitary safety and prevent possible future outbreaks.

- 01** Continuous and automatic pathogen monitoring.
- 02** Detection of known diseases and unknown viruses.
- 03** Early warning of risks.